

Modernizing Quezon City's Building Risk Data with AI and Earth Observation

Joshua Dimasaka¹, Fouad Bendimerad², Renan Ma. Tanhueco³, Christian Geiß⁴, Emily So⁵

ABSTRACT

Developing, maintaining, updating, and forecasting city-scale building risk data is costly yet essential for tracking progress toward the UN Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030. Although advances in information technology and big data have enabled a shift from low- to high-resolution mapping, current state-of-practice methods remain limited in detail and accuracy due to the challenges in coarse-to-fine-grained mapping across spatiotemporal scales. To address these challenges, we develop a novel spatiotemporal framework that integrates the rich information from time-series Earth Observation data and leverages recent advances in artificial intelligence, including graph deep learning, state-space modeling, and probabilistic inference. Through an academic research collaboration with Earthquakes and Megacities Initiative (EMI) and Quezon City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (QCDRRMO), we present a flexible probabilistic framework and an open-access dataset comprising annual spatiotemporal 10-meter maps of building exposure and physical vulnerability for Quezon City, Philippines, from 2016 to 2030, along with associated uncertainty estimates. Beyond demonstrating the potential of AI and Earth Observation in modernizing building risk data, our work has offered a dynamic approach to disaster risk auditing by capturing spatiotemporal changes in exposure and vulnerability, thereby empowering local governments with data-driven insights for effective disaster risk reduction.

Keywords: probabilistic, regional risk, machine learning, exposure, vulnerability, Earth Observation

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2022, the Earthquakes and Megacities Initiative (EMI) and the government of Quezon City conducted its climate and disaster risk assessment using an improved geospatial building exposure and physical vulnerability database (EMI, 2022), combining another prior study (Allen et al., 2014) and a high-resolution digital elevation map.

With the increasing availability of Earth Observation data and rapid advancement in artificial intelligence techniques, we extend the 2022 assessment using the annually aggregated 10-meter maps of publicly available Sentinel 2 multispectral imagery (Copernicus Sentinel data, 2025a, 2025b), proximity to road networks, and temporal building height data from Google Open Buildings 2.5D Temporal (Sirko et al., 2023).

Combining graph deep learning, state-space modeling, and variational inference using time-series data and prior expert belief systems in a weakly supervised or coarse-to-fine-grained manner (Dimasaka et al., 2025a, 2025b), we probabilistically infer and forecast the likelihood of

¹ Joshua Dimasaka is a PhD candidate with a professional background in civil engineering, public policy, and data science at the UKRI CDT in the Application of Artificial Intelligence to the study of Environmental Risks (AI4ER) and Cambridge University Centre for Risk in the Built Environment (CURBE).

² Fouad Bendimerad is the Chairman at Earthquakes and Megacities Initiative (EMI) and has served as consultant and advisor on risk management to several international organizations and corporations.

³ Renan Ma. Tanhueco is the Vice Chair for Program Development at Earthquakes and Megacities Initiative (EMI) and an Associate Professor of Civil Engineering at De La Salle University in the Philippines.

⁴ Christian Geiß leads the Georisks group at the Earth Observation Center of the German Aerospace Center and is a University Professor at the University of Bonn.

⁵ Emily So is a chartered civil engineer and Director of the Cambridge University Centre for Risk in the Built Environment (CURBE). She is currently the Deputy Head of the School of Arts and Humanities and an Associate Director of the Open-Oxford-Cambridge AHRC Doctoral Training Partnership.

EXTENDED ABSTRACTS

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each physical vulnerability class at finer-grained spatial resolution and annual attribution from 2016 to 2030 using the learned city-wide dynamics of urban development and interdependencies from various Earth Observation data.

II. METHODOLOGY AND FINDINGS

This work used the comprehensively validated data, developed by EMI (2022), in coordination with the Quezon City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (QCRRMO) for scientific research purposes only.

We introduce Graph Variational State-Space Model (GraphVSSM), a novel spatiotemporal framework that uniquely addresses the unstructured data of built environment, limited historical observations, and variational inference for categorical probabilistic modelling of building typology classes (Dimasaka et al., 2025a). Among its modular components, we further describe the exposure-to-vulnerability modelling as Graph Categorical Structured Variational Autoencoder (GraphCSVAE), which has also been applied to other case studies in Bangladesh and Sierra Leone for post-disaster analyses (Dimasaka et al., 2025b).

For an overview of findings, we show that examining the derived posterior parameters of our GraphVSSM reveals insights into the regional spatiotemporal dynamics of building exposure and physical vulnerability. Our findings also demonstrate that incorporating prior knowledge into the learning optimization task to address weak multi-class supervision allows the GraphVSSM to balance supervised learning with deep probabilistic coarse-to-fine-grained updating (Dimasaka et al., 2025a).

Given the page limitation of this extended abstract, further details and results are provided in the accompanying preprints.

III. CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEP

Relevant to key local decision makers in monitoring the efforts to reduce disaster risk, our work demonstrates a city-wide spatiotemporal updating or auditing of the existing building exposure and physical vulnerability database, aided by advanced machine learning techniques and satellite imagery. For future work, we recommend the incorporation of building-level information, even sparse or incomplete, in achieving more accurate higher-order analyses.

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EXTENDED ABSTRACTS

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